

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF CROHN'S DISEASE-A CASE STUDY**1)DR . RADHIKA SHARMA****ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR (PANCHAKARMA)****BABE KE AYURVED MEDICAL COLLEGE (PUNJAB)****2)DR VINOD ADE****PROFESSOR (PANCHAKARMA)****MGAC &RH**

Crohn's disease is a Chronic Idiopathy inflammatory bowel disease characterized by skip lesion and transmural inflammation that can affect the entire G.I tract from mouth till anus . It primarily causes ulcerations (breaks in the lining) of the small and large intestines, but can affect the digestive system It causes a wide variety of symptoms like abdominal pain, diarrhoea (even bloody if inflammation is severe), vomiting, weight loss. It may also cause complications outside the gastrointestinal tract such as skin rashes, arthritis, and inflammation of the eye, tiredness, and lack of concentration. Crohn's disease is related closely to another chronic inflammatory condition that involves only the colon called ulcerative colitis. Together, Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis are frequently referred to as inflammatory bowel disease (IBD).

Crohn's disease is caused by interactions between environmental, immunological and bacterial factors in genetically susceptible individuals. This result in a chronic inflammatory disorder, in which the body's immune system attacks the gastrointestinal tract possibly directed at microbial antigens. Crohn's disease has traditionally been described as an autoimmune disease, but recent investigators have described it as an immune deficiency state.

According to Ayurveda, Crohn's can be compared with '*Raktaj Grahani*' disease. *Grahani* in Ayurveda, is actually an anatomical term to describe small intestines (specifically Ileum and jejunam). Any vitiation or inflammation to this particular part by imbalanced Doshas (Vata, Pitta, Kapha) can cause a wide variety of symptom similar to that of Crohn's disease, anywhere across the digestive system. Degree and nature of symptoms may vary as per the doshic predominance & involvement.

At CHARAKA, we are providing very effective treatment for Crohn's disease based on the classical principle of Ayurveda and our research. Treatment involves internal research medicines, strict diet regime and life style modifications. In more severe and chronic cases, Panchakarma therapy is selectively done along with these. Pichha Basti indicated in Parvahika, Grahani and Atisara by Acharya Charaka and Vagbatta. This Basti reduce inflammation due to its Grahi, Deepandravya and Picchila Guna

KEYWORDS:- Crohn's disease,Grahani,Picchabasti,Ayurveda.

Crohn's disease tends to present initially in the teens and twenties, with another peak incidence in the fifties to seventies, although the disease can occur at any age. Males and females are equally affected. Smokers are two times more likely to develop Crohn's disease than non-smokers. Crohn's disease tends to be more common in relatives of patients with Crohn's disease. If a person has a relative with the disease, his/her risk of developing the disease is estimated to be at least 10 times that of the general population and 30 times greater if the relative with Crohn's disease is a sibling.

Treatment options are restricted to controlling symptoms, maintaining remission, and preventing relapse. The disease was named after gastroenterologist Burrill Bernard Crohn, who, in 1932, together with two other colleagues at Mount Sinai Hospital in New York, described a series of patients with inflammation of the terminal ileum, the area most commonly affected by the illness.¹ Ayurveda, the holistic science of India, places a lot of emphasis of the care of the digestive system.

The Ayurvedic concepts particularly focus on the significance of healthy digestive system with regard to the overall balanced functioning and healthiness of the human body and mind. Healthy digestion ensures that the nutrients taken in through food are able to produce healthy tissues (Saptha Dhathus). When digestion is weak, the tissues of your body – including muscle, blood, bone and nerves – become weak and susceptible to disease. Various Panchakarma treatments of modalities for the management of these diseases are mentioned in our classics Pichha Basti is best among there²

AIM AND OBJECTIVE:-

To evaluate to efficacy of modified Pichha Basti in the management of crohn's disease

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selection and source of Patient was registered from OPD of Panchkarma department and admitted in general IPD ward .

Plan of study – The drug required for Basti Karma were procured and prepared in Prakalpa of Panchkarma theatre.

outdoor basis for 4 weeks.The treatment given was:

- 1.Tab. Cologrit 2Bd
- 2.Tab. Kutaj ghan vati 2Bd
- 3.Piccha vasti for 1week

CASE STUDY-

A married female patient age of 45 years, Hindu house wife, graduate, economic status is lower middle, visited OPD on date Complaining of blood with faeces, abdomen pain, mucus discharge and generalised weakness since 1 year. The incidence occurred after every 3-4days.

The patient took allopathic treatment for more than 1year but got no satisfactory relief. The patient visited Patanjali wellness center Haridwar for treatment and took indoor treatment for 2weeks and got mild relief.

Personal history No family history along with no history of any other major illness such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus,

tuberculosis, Hyperthyroidism, liver disease etc. No history of any type of past surgery. Had vegetarian diet with regular

food habit, frequently eating salty, spice, bitter oily food.

General physical examination

Temperature - 37°C

- Pulse rate - 78/min
- Respiratory rate - 18/min
- Blood pressure - 120/80mmHg
- Weight - 60 kg
- Height - 5.3ft

Systemic examination

- GIT - pain and tenderness in lower abdomen.
- Respiratory – NAD
- Cardiovascular-NAD

Criteria for inclusion-

Sign and symptoms of crohn's disease

Parameters Subjective parameters

- Bowel frequency with loose stool.
- Abdominal pain.
- Blood with stool.
- Weakness.
- Loss of weight

Ashtavidha Pariksha (eight-fold examination)-

- Pulse rate - 78/min, Rhythm - Regular, volume - normal, tension - normal, force - normal.
- Stool - Appearance - bloody mixed stool defecation.
- Urine - Amount - 5 to 8 times/day and one time at night.

- Tongue - Normal in shape & sized
- Touch - Afebrile ▪ Eye - Normal in vision
- Appearance – Medium
- Voice - Normal voice with clarity.

Dashavidha Pariksha (ten-fold examination)-

1. Prakriti - Vata-Pittaja 2. Vikriti - Dosha-Dushya Samoocchana 3. Sara - Madhyama 4. Samhanana - Madhyama 5. Pramana - Madhyama 6. Satva - Madhyama 7. Saatmya - Madhyama 8. Ahara-Shakti - Aawara 9. Vyayaam Shakti – Aawara 10. Vaya- Madhyama Srotas examination

STROTAS PAIKSHA

1. Pranavaha Srotus – NAD
2. Udakavaha Srotas – NAD
3. Annavaha Srotas - Avipaka (indigestion)
4. Rasavaha Srotas – NAD
5. Raktavaha Srotas – NAD
6. Mansvaha Srotas – NAD
7. Medovaha Srotas - Alasya (lethargy)
8. Ashtivaha Srotas - NAD
9. Majjavaha Srotas - NAD
10. Shukravaha Srotas – NAD
11. Manovaha Srotas - NAD

12. Artavaha Srotas - NAD
13. Mootravaha Srotas – NAD
14. Purishavaha Srotas - Raktvayukta Purish Tyaga (blood mixed stool defecation)
15. Swedavaha Srotas – NAD

Assessment criteria:

Improvement was assessed on the basis of relief in subjective and objective parameters.

1. Bowel frequency

0	1 or 2 times in a day
1	3 or 4 times in a day
2	5 or 7 times in a day
3	8 or 12 times in a day
4	More than 12 times a day

2. Blood in stool

0	No bleeding
1	Occasional bleeding in stool (not daily)
2	Bleeding daily but less than 4 times / day
3	Bleeding daily but less than 8 times /day
4	Bleeding daily but more than 8 times /day

Treatment plan Piccha Basti

[1.] Poorva Karma - Sarwang Snehana Swedana with Moorhit Tila Tail and Mrudu Vashpa Swedana.

[2.] Pardhan Karma - Patient was made to lie in left lateral position for administration of Basti.

Content of Piccha Basti:-³

[3] a) Salmali Vrinta Kashaya b) Ghrita c) Madhu (honey)

d) Kalka Darvya ▪ Manjista Choorna ▪ Mocharasa Choorna ▪ Lodhra Choorna ▪ Nagkeser Choorna ▪ Yastimadhu choorna ▪ Rasanjan Choorna Other Requirements ▪ Syringe ▪ Catheter 8 no. ▪ Gloves

Method of preparation of Piccha Basti:-⁴

To prepare the mixture for decoction enema. One must follow a sequence of mixing various ingredients. First add honey and rock salt and mix properly than add ghee, again mixing properly than add to be fine Manjisthadi Kalka of herbs and finally add to it Shalmali Vrintadi Kashaya. The whole mixture when thoroughly mixed. Should be heated to body. Temperature over water vapour then pours these contents into an enema pot.

Duration of Treatment:-

The patient got satisfactory relief after 5th day .And the incidence of bleeding reduced to 1 incidence after 4-5 day. The treatment was continued for next 14 days along with Nabhi vasti.After 10th day their was no incidence of bleeding for next 10days .After that the treatment was continued for next 7days.And there was no incidence of bleeding per rectum. The patient was feeling very much relief in general well-being. After that the treatment was continued and the patient was advised Piccha vasti twice weekly. And there was no incidence of bleeding for next 2 weeks. After that Vasti was stopped and the patient was advised to take oral treatment for next 2 weeks.

3. Pashchata Karma:-

- a) Patient is asked to keep lying for 3-4 minutes for better absorption of Basti drug.
- b) Patient is advised to take light diet.
- c) Patient is advised to avoid fast foods and spicy foods. advised to follow the Sansarjan Karma.

Duration of follow up Periods: -15 days

DISCUSSION:-

Many people with Crohn's disease have symptoms for years prior to the diagnosis. Because of the 'patchy' nature of the gastrointestinal disease and the depth of tissue involvement, initial symptoms can be more subtle than those of ulcerative colitis. People with Crohn's disease experience chronic recurring periods of flare-ups and remission. Various types of Basti Karma are mentioned in classics based on their action one among them is Pichha Basti. It is named of its Pichhila property which means sticky or lubricant in nature Because of this Property it forms a protective layer over the intestinal mucosa to avoid friction and reduction intestinal irritation. The ingredients used in Pichha Vasti were Salmali Niryasa, Ghrita, Taila, Madhu and Dugdha. All ingredients are having similar properties like Madhura Rasa, Sheeta Veerya and Madhura Paka.

MODE OF ACTION:-

- Shothahara and Vrana Ropaka (Anti Inflammatory and Ulcer Healing).
- Raktasthambhaka (Haemostatic Agent)
- Sangrahi / Stambhan (Anti Diarrheal & Anti Dysenteries)
- Pitta Shamaka
- Agnideepaka

CONCLUSION:-

Piccha Piccha Basti was prepared from easily available herbs and after administration gave good symptomatic relief. Sangrahi and Sodhana property of Piccha Basti facilitate healing in colon mucosa. Usually results are very good with Ayurvedic line of treatment. Early cases tend to respond quickly than chronic. If patient can stick to all the guidelines as advised, even complete cure can also be achieved.

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